

ALTERNATING PROBABILITY: THE THEORY OF GENETIC ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

Genetic engineering or studying about human genes with modified effects is a major source of research in now a day. Although its not feasible to make a genetically engineered human, but apart from us, it has been applied to other flora or fauna. To alter the DNA or the foundation of the very genes has an impact to the engineered species. However, as it has been possible to study the behavior of finding whether the developed or superior model has been beneficial to humanity or harmful after the growth of the being, this paper has been aimed to discuss, whether before the mutation, it has been possible or not to predict the outcomes of the behaviors' of the superior engineered beings. As this have been a source of several Sci-fi movies, so, to calculate the proximity of the mutation, we have to depend on the probability theory whether the being has been engineered good or whether it has bad effects. We will continue in detail with appropriate logic and mathematics as we proceed through the paper. The main object of this paper is to interpret the reality of the engineered humans in view or perspective of mathematics.

METHODOLOGY AND INTERPRETATION

When any human has been genetically modified or engineered then there exists two initial states namely Σ_1 and Σ_2 and a final state Σ . The human before mutation is in state Σ_1 and the genetic change that needs to be altered are in state Σ_2 while the engineered being is in a final state Σ . Has it been possible to know what the final state Σ be from the set of two initial states Σ_1 and Σ_2 ? Well, as far as we can assume that the final state actually depends on the mutation factor of the second initial state Σ_2 as if Σ_2 is superior then Σ becomes superior and if Σ_2 becomes inferior then Σ will become inferior but as we will see that it's not the case. The final output Σ that will be derived after mutation will either be inferior or be superior and this actually depends upon the Probability factor that we are going to discuss below.

Consider the Set Σ_1 and Σ_2 separately.

$$\Sigma_1 = \{\varphi\}$$

$$\Sigma_2 = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \sigma_4\}$$

From here Σ_1 has only 1 factors and as the factor is null, so, it won't ideally make any changes alone but if it interact with Σ_2 then the various probabilities will emerge with a Probability factor $\frac{1}{4}$.

That is....

$$\Sigma \Rightarrow \Sigma_1 * \Sigma_2 = \{\varphi\sigma_1, \varphi\sigma_2, \varphi\sigma_3, \varphi\sigma_4\}$$

So, let's explain the 4 Probabilities now...

$$\text{Case 1} = \Sigma = \{\varphi\sigma_1\}$$

$$\text{Case 2} = \Sigma = \{\varphi\sigma_2\}$$

$$\text{Case 3} = \Sigma = \{\varphi\sigma_3\}$$

$$\text{Case 4} = \Sigma = \{\varphi\sigma_4\}$$

Case 1 represents the genetically engineered human with a superior being.

Case 2 represents the genetically engineered human with an inferior being.

Case 3 represents the genetically represented human with the average identity like $(\varphi\sigma_1 + \varphi\sigma_2)/2$

Case 4 represents the genetically engineered human with a failed probability or dead.

So, to interpret from the end **Case 4** is a failed Probability or collapsed Probability.

While **Case 3** is of no use to humans as it's just like the average humans.

But **Case 2** becomes an inferior quality which is harmful to humans and destructive in nature.

And **Case 1** is the most successful with a superior quality that is both constructive and beneficial to humans.

One important thing to note is that there exists a mutual mathematical and also Physiological relationship between the first 3 Cases while Case 4 is Distinct (collapsed case) like...

Inclusion and Exclusion Set $\rightarrow \{(Case 1 \cap Case 2 \cap Case 3), (Case 4) \mid (Case 1 \cap Case 2 \cap Case 3 \text{ is inclusive while Case 4 is exclusive})\}$

CONCLUSION

It's impossible to know the probability of the mutation before its being happened. There always lies a Probability factor of $\frac{1}{4}$. This is not because of Σ_1 but because of the combination of $\Sigma_1 * \Sigma_2$ which is 4 factors of Σ . Among the two initial states, the pure state Σ_1 has nothing to contribute while the dependable state of the mutation Σ_2 combines with the Pure State Σ_1 and makes all the happenings. However, it's difficult to judge from the 4 Final states that which 1 ($\frac{1}{4}$ Probability) will dominate in the final states. The dominant states can be purely beneficial and superior if the Probability reduces to 1 if we can eliminate the last 3 Cases. But it's impossible to predict what will be the final output. So, the equation that needs to be satisfied to make Σ as a beneficial mutant state of extreme superiority is...

$$\Sigma = \varphi\sigma_{1,2,3,4} - \varphi\sigma_{2,3,4}$$

Its difficult to eliminate a Probability factor but if it can be eliminated then the world as we know will be changed forever with lots of intelligent mutants all across the globe helping less superior humans (like us) in the betterment of living.